

SILICA DEPOSITION TREATMENT FOR IMPROVING ADHESION PROPERTIES OF ADHESIVE BONDING OR COATING OF AIRCRAFTS

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ABSTRACT

Surface treatment is important to ensure adhesion properties of adhesive bonding or coating. Although laser irradiation or atmospheric plasma treatment has attracted as innovative surface treatment in aviation industry, silica deposition treatment could be another choice to improve adhesion properties of aircraft structural applications such as adhesive bonding joints or coating. The silica deposition treatment is a kind of flame treatment which uses liquid petroleum gas containing silane compounds as combusting feed, and could be quick, easy, clean and costless process. In this study, mechanical strength properties of the silica deposition treatment were investigated. Two kinds of testing were conducted. One is single lap tensile tests of adhesively-bonded joints using carbon/epoxy composites or titanium alloys. The results of the tests indicated lap shear strength increased as the number of passes increased. The 12 times passing coupons of both of composites and titanium alloys exhibited high strength comparable to the conventional treatment coupons. The other is coating adhesion pull-off tests using aluminum alloys. Just only one-time pass brought high adhesion comparable to the conventional treatment. This means, as for aluminum coating application, the silica deposition treatment might be beneficial treatment in actual production scene compared with conventional ways.

1 INTRODUCTION

Surface treatment is important process to realize high mechanical performance of adhesive bonding or coating. In recent years, composite airframes become common and it expands application of adhesively-bonded joints. Nevertheless, surface treatment process for adhesively-bonded joints is still carried out manually or releases hazardous chemicals. Improvement of surface treatment process—treating quickly, easily, cleanly, and less costly—reduces fabrication costs and environmental burden. In addition to that, improvement of surface treatment also contributes to reduce costs and environmental burden of aircraft coating process.

Laser irradiation or atmospheric plasma treatment has attracted as innovative surface treatment in aviation industry and many researchers have studied joint properties or performance with those new treatments [1-9]. However, most of the studies are focused on composite materials though actual aircraft structures utilize a variety of materials such as composites, aluminum alloys, titanium alloys and steels. Titanium alloys are major materials in the case of bi-material bonding with composites. In addition, aluminum alloys are still major structural materials of airframes, and protective coating or repainting is carried out onto them. Surface treatment studies therefore should be scoped not only composites but also metals.

We had investigated several different surface treating methods provided by private suppliers, and a couple of methods exhibited good performance (mechanical performance and wettability) for titanium alloys [10]. Among them, we focused on the silica deposition treatment (trade name: ITRO Treatment) as quick, easy, clean and reasonable process. This treatment has been applied such as automotive parts treatment or label bonding treatment on glass bottles whereas it has not been applied in aviation industry so far.

In this study, effects of the silica deposition treatment on mechanical performance was investigated. Two types of test pieces were prepared according to applications. One is adhesively-bonded single lap joint coupons using carbon/epoxy composite or titanium alloy and lap shear strength was measured. The other is coating test pieces using aluminum alloy and pull-off strength was measured.

2 SILICA DEPOSITION TREATMENT

The silica deposition treatment (Fig. 1) in this study is a kind of flame treatment. We used “ITRO treatment” as the silica deposition treatment provided by Nakata Coating Co., Ltd. in Japan or Nakata U.S.A., Ltd. in the United States. Liquid petroleum gas (LPG) containing silane compounds is combusted and silicon oxide (SiO_2) film is formed onto treated surfaces. The film consists of nano-order silica particles (Fig. 2).

The variables of this treatment are, for example, the ratio of gas to air, the gas/air flow rate, the concentration of silane compounds, the distance from the sample surface to the flame burner, the scan speed, and the number of passes by the burner. In this study, the number of passes (N)—in other words, the number of treating—is variable and other parameters are fixed. The number of passes is associated with the amount of silica deposition.

Figure 1: The silica deposition treatment. This picture shows the treatment with a portable gas flame gun, whereas the treatment with a fixed type burner (no picture), which is easy to control the treatment variables, was applied in this study.

Figure 2: A scanning electron microscope image of the silica deposition condition onto carbon/epoxy composites. Formed silica film is aggregation of nano-particles and looked like random mosaic pattern or speckle pattern.

3 EXPERIMENT

In this study, two types of testing were carried out to evaluate effects of the silica deposition treatment. One is tensile shear strength tests and adhesively-bonded single lap joints were prepared as the test coupons. The other is pull-off tests, which can measure adhesion strength of coating. Details are described in the following subsections.

3.1 Test pieces and test method for adhesive bonding application

Adhesively-bonded single lap joint testing was planned on the basis of ASTM D3165-00. Carbon/epoxy composite (T800S/3900-2B, Toray Industries, Inc.) and titanium alloy (Ti-6Al-4V, AMS4911) were prepared as the substrate materials in this study. Carbon/epoxy composite laminates (quasi-isotropic laminates, [45/0/-45/90]_s) as the substrates were cured in advance prior to fabricate test coupons. The test coupons (Fig. 3) were fabricated by bonding the substrates of the same materials using film adhesive (Metlbond 1515-3, Cytac Industries Inc.). In other words, composite/composite adhesively-bonded joints and titanium alloy/titanium alloy adhesively-bonded joints were fabricated.

The substrate surfaces were degreased by methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) prior to the silica deposition treatment. After that, the silica deposition treatment ($N=0, 6, 12$) was carried out onto the substrate surfaces of film adhesive side. Here, $N=0$ means the silica deposition treatment is not carried out. In addition, the mechanical abrasion treatment for the composites and the chemical conversion treatment for the titanium alloy were applied as reference treatments. These treatments are common ways in aviation industry.

Hydraulic testing machine (Instron 8802, Illinois Tool Works Inc.) was used to measure tensile lap shear strength of the test coupons. The lap shear strength (S_L) is derived from the following equation:

$$S_L = P_F/lb \quad (1)$$

where l is the overlap length (12.7 mm), b is the coupon width (25.4 mm), and P_F is the failure load.

Figure 3: Single lap test coupon configuration. The large bonded sandwich panel ($\approx 254 \times 254 \text{ mm}^2$) are initially fabricated, then the panel is cut and grooved to shape the test coupons by machining.

3.2 Test Pieces and test method for coating application

There are several test methods to obtain adhesion strength of coating. Among them, pull-off testing can obtain adhesion strength quantitatively. In this study, pull-off testing based on ISO4624 was carried out. aluminum alloy (cladded 2024-T3, AMS-QQ-A-250/5) was prepared as the substrate material. Test pieces are the coated sheets ($\approx 305 \times 305 \text{ mm}^2$, thickness is 1.27 mm) of the aluminum alloy.

Test pieces were prepared as follows. First the substrate surfaces were degreased by MEK. Then, the silica deposition treatment ($N=0, 1, 6, 12$) was carried out onto the surfaces. After that, the epoxy primer (CA7233, PPG Industries, Inc.) was applied as coating. The process of coating was in accordance with MIL-PRF-23377. In addition, the chromic acid anodizing treatment (MIL-A-8625 Type I Class 1, hot water seal) was applied as reference treatment, which is common treatment in aviation industry.

The adhesion tester (PosiTest AT-A, DeFelsko Corporation) was used to measure pull-off adhesion strength. Figure 4 shows a picture of test execution. The dollies, which have a role of interface fitting between the test piece and the loading module, are bonded to the test pieces by the epoxy adhesive (DP410, 3M company). Tensile load is perpendicularly applied to the direction of out of plane. The

pull-off strength (S_P) is derived from the following equation:

$$S_P = P_F/A \quad (2)$$

where A is the bonded area of the dolly (314 mm²) and P_F is the failure load.

For the purpose of evaluating effects of the silica deposition treatment, failure should occur along the treated interface, that is, boundary between the coating and the substrate. If the fracture surfaces do not correspond to the treated interfaces, the results of that are treated as invalid in this study (Fig. 5).

Figure 4: A picture of pull-off test execution. The diameter of the dolly is 20 mm (namely, bonded area of 314 mm²). Tensile load is perpendicularly applied by means of air pressure. Yellow-green color of the test piece is the color of the epoxy primer.

Figure 5: A cross section of the test piece around the dolly. (a) Composition around the dolly. (b) When the fracture surface corresponds to the treated interface, that is valid to evaluate effects of the silica deposition treatment on adhesion strength. (c), (d) If not, the results are treated as invalid.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Test results of the adhesively-bonded joints

Figure 6 and 7 are the lap shear strength (average of 5 test results for each condition) of the carbon/epoxy composite joint coupons and of the titanium alloy joint coupons, respectively. These results indicated the number of passes (N) is the key parameter to reinforce the lap shear strength. The $N=12$ coupons of both the composite and the titanium alloy exhibited high strength comparable to that of the reference treatment coupons.

Pictures of the fracture surfaces after the single lap tensile tests are indicated in Fig. 8. The surfaces of $N=0$ indicated perfect adhesive failure for both substrates. Regarding the carbon/epoxy composite coupons, the silica-deposited coupons ($N=6$ and $N=12$) mainly indicated substrate failure (fiber-tear failure) and the reference coupons indicated similar appearance as well. That means the silica deposition treatment brought enough adhesion strength between the adhesive and the substrate. The substrate failure area within the fracture surfaces of $N=12$ is somewhat larger than that of $N=6$. The lap

shear strength (Fig. 6) is also the same trend. Regarding the titanium alloy coupons, differences of appearance are easily distinguished compared with the composite coupons. The fracture surfaces are composed of the adhesive area (blue color) and the metal area (gray color) and observed somewhat adhesive residue left on the metal area. Focusing on the residue, which seems to be a result of cohesive failure, the $N=6$ coupons left residue a little but the $N=12$ coupons left residue a lot comparable to the reference coupons. That is consistent with what the silica deposition treatment of $N=12$ had enough adhesion strength compared with the reference treatment.

Figure 6: The lap shear strength of the carbon/epoxy composite with the silica deposition onto the surfaces. Error bars are standard deviation. The reference treatment in this figure is the mechanical abrasion treatment.

Figure 7: The lap shear strength of Ti-6Al-4V with the silica deposition onto the surfaces. Error bars are standard deviation. The reference treatment in this figure is the chemical conversion treatment.

Figure 8: Fracture surfaces of (a) the carbon/epoxy composite joint coupons and (b) the titanium alloy joint coupons. The blue color in these pictures is the color of film adhesive.

4.2 Test results of the coating adhesion

Figure 9 shows the pull-off strength (average of 5 valid results for each condition) of the aluminum alloy coating test pieces. Just only one-time pass ($N=1$) brought high strength comparable to the reference treatment test pieces. This means, as for aluminum coating application, the silica deposition treatment might be the quicker and easier treatment in actual production scene compared with conventional ways.

Sample images of the fracture surfaces of the pull-off tests are indicated in Fig. 10. The surfaces of $N=0$ indicated perfect adhesive failure whereas the other conditions left residue of some kind on the fracture surfaces. The fracture surfaces of $N=6$ and $N=12$ were covered with whitish thin film which is considered deposited silica. The surfaces of $N=1$ were hard to recognize the thin film visually. However, the pull-off strength of $N=1$ was comparable to the reference. Deposited silica may affect bonding reinforcement even one-time pass treatment.

Figure 9: The coating adhesion strength (pull-off strength) of cladded 2024-T3 with the silica deposition onto the surfaces. Error bars are standard deviation. The reference treatment in this figure is the chromic acid anodizing treatment.

Figure 10: Fracture surfaces of the adhesion tests. Yellow-green is the color of the epoxy primer. Gray color in (a) is the color of anodized substrate surfaces.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The silica deposition treatment could be another choice to improve adhesion properties of aircraft structural applications such as adhesive bonding joints or coating although laser irradiation or atmospheric plasma treatment has attracted as innovative surface treatment in aviation industry. Besides, the silica deposition treatment is expected to be quick, easy, clean, and costless treatment. In this study, the silica deposition treatment was applied as surface treatment to adhesive bonding and coating, and then, mechanical strength properties—namely, lap shear strength and pull-off strength—were investigated. The findings of this study are as follows:

- Regarding the lap shear strength of the carbon/epoxy composite joints and of the titanium alloy joints, the number of passes (N) is the key parameter to reinforce the lap shear strength. The strength of $N=12$ exhibited high strength comparable to that of the mechanical abrasion (for the composite) or the chemical conversion treatment (for the titanium alloy).
- Regarding the adhesion pull-off strength of the aluminium alloy coating test pieces, the strength with one-time treatment ($N=1$) reached that with the chromic acid anodizing treatment.

The silica deposition treatment could be considered as one of options to realize quick, easy, clean and reasonable surface treatment process for adhesive bonding or coating.

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